

**THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT, PRICE, PLACE, AND PROMOTION
ON SME COMPETITIVENESS: EVIDENCE FROM UD SANJAYA DRY
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Abstract

The business sector in Indonesia has developed from the use of complex strategies, competition, change and uncertainty. The goal is to find out the implementation that must be carried out in order to compete in the global market. Especially in Natar District, South Lampung Regency, Lampung Province at UD Sanjaya Dry Noodle SMEs. The advantages possessed by UD Sanjaya are having quality ingredients, modern production equipment and having a variety of snack products. Marketing mix is a marketing strategy that has seven elements (7P) in the form of products, prices, promotions, distribution, processes, officers and physical support that aim to achieve organizational goals. This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach. Qualitative research is a type of research that aims to understand and analyze a phenomenon, problem. This method focuses on collecting data such as interviews, observations, field notes, and document analysis to provide a clear and comprehensive picture of the situation or context at the time of the study. It can be concluded from the (7P) studied that promotions on social media can also increase UD Sanjaya's marketing targets.

Keywords: Marketing Strategy, Marketing Mix, Competitive Advantage, SME.**1. Introduction**

The business sector in Indonesia has developed from the use of complex strategies, competition, change and uncertainty. Every business actor will not be free from business competition. Strategy is defined as the determination of a plan by a manager accompanied by the preparation of a method or effort that is similar to the long term of the organization. Strategy is defined as an ongoing action and is implemented based on what customers want in the future. The development of Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) is called an achievement, especially for countries with low per capita. Indonesian SME contributed 60% to 90% of GDP in 2019. In 2023, the number of Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) in Indonesia will reach 66,103,391 units. The SME sector in Indonesia is very broad not only in terms of the number of business units, but also in its contribution to job creation. The development and empowerment of this sector is very important because it supports sustainable and inclusive economic growth in Indonesia. The role of Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) in accelerating economic growth is very important, because of its contribution to the balance of payments

through export activities and its ability to absorb a number of workers, namely 70% of the total number of workers in Indonesia.

Companies can choose to compete, starting with relatively cheap prices or by improving the quality of their products. If a company's price is high, then the company should improve the quality of its products to win the competition. The marketing mix is also commonly referred to as the marketing mix. Marketing mix is a marketing strategy that has seven elements (7P) in the form of products, prices, promotions, distribution, processes, officers and physical support that aim to achieve organizational goals. One of them is reflected in the stability of sales levels from one year to the next, according to the quality of the products that can be produced by the company. UD Sanjaya is a Small and Medium Enterprise (SME) engaged in snacks. So the researcher wants to conduct research on Dry Noodle products at the UD Sanjaya Company. To find out how the marketing mix strategy carried out by the owner of the UD Sanjaya Company has become a company that is still standing today and can compete with other types (SME) businesses.

2. Theoretical Background

Marketing mix strategy is an important element in marketing management to create value for consumers and win the competition in the market. Kotler & Keller (2016) show that effective mix management can create competitive advantage by responding to customer needs better than competitors.

Competitive advantage is defined as a company's ability to provide superior and sustainable value, either product differentiation, profitability or broad market access (Porter 1985). Previous research shows a close relationship between the implementation of the right marketing mix strategy and increased competitiveness. For example, a study by Rachmawati (2020) shows that a combination of digital promotion strategies and competitive pricing increases customer loyalty in SME. Meanwhile, research by Wijaya (2019) identified that product innovation in the "product" element has a significant impact on consumer preferences in the processed food industry.

The marketing mix consists of four main elements, often referred to as the 4Ps: product, price, place, and promotion (Kotler & Keller, 2016). The "product" element relates to the company's ability to develop quality products that meet consumer expectations (Wijaya, 2019). Product innovation is one of the key factors in achieving sustainable competitive advantage, as supported by the study of Wijaya (2019), which found that companies that frequently update their product offerings tend to attract more consumers. The "price" element refers to the pricing strategy that aligns with customer willingness to pay while maintaining profitability. According to Monroe (2003), pricing significantly influences customer perceptions of value, which affects their purchasing decisions.

The "place" element covers distribution channels and logistics to ensure product availability in the right locations. Effective distribution can expand market reach and enhance customer satisfaction (Christopher, 2016). The "promotion" element involves various strategies such as advertising, sales promotions, digital marketing, and

personal selling, which are crucial in building brand awareness and customer engagement (Kotler & Armstrong, 2018).

In the context of increasingly tight business competition, especially in the MSME sector such as UD Sanjaya, which is engaged in the dry noodle industry, the implementation of a marketing mix strategy becomes very relevant (Porter, 1985). The main issue raised is how companies can utilize each element of the marketing mix to not only increase sales but also create sustainable competitive advantage. By focusing on product innovation, competitive pricing, effective distribution, and targeted promotion, it is expected that the company will be able to face the challenges of competition while meeting customer expectations (Rachmawati, 2020; Wijaya, 2019). Through this analysis, the study aims to identify the best strategies that can be adopted to support business sustainability and the company's competitiveness in the market (Kotler & Keller, 2016). A proper understanding and application of the marketing mix will enable businesses to create superior value propositions and strengthen their position in the industry (Kotler & Keller, 2016; Porter, 1985).

3. Methods

This study employs a qualitative approach to holistically understand phenomena through descriptions, utilizing methods such as interviews, observations, field notes, and document analysis. The research focuses on the 7P marketing mix and competitive advantages at UD Sanjaya, located in Candimas Village, South Lampung. Data collection involved direct observation, interviews with relevant informants, and documentation. The findings were derived from analyzing these data sources to draw conclusions about the research context.

3.1 Marketing Strategy

A marketing strategy is a series of points and targets. Regulations and policies to place direction on the company's marketing efforts from time to time, at each level, focus and provision, first for the company's response to the ever-changing competitive atmosphere and climate (Jeplyansyah & Oktaviannur, 2022).

3.2 Marketing Mix

According to (Wibowo et al., 2015) Marketing Mix is a collection of tactical marketing tools used by companies to get the response they want in the market. The marketing mix consists of seven variables called the "Seven Ps".

3.3 Product

(Haryono & Marniyati, 2018) said that a product is a collection of tools that are clearly defined in a form. In general, a product is one of the tangible and intangible tools that include color, packaging, accurate retail prices and factory services at retailers that can be accepted by buyers as something that can provide desires to customers. According to (Purwiantoro et al., 2016) explains that quality products can create customer satisfaction.

3.4 Price

According to (Dwimala & Maimunah, 1970) price is the highest and lowest value of a product, depending on the quality of the product. with the quality of the product in question.

3.5 Promotion

In (Aribah et al., 2014) Promotion is a marketing strategy that can be shown to inform or convince consumers about the use of a product or service by persuading them to buy products or services from the company at the right price.

3.6 Place

According to (Izannah & Widiartanto, 2020) states that place or location is not the only factor in influencing place, but also affects the distribution of the right channels to reach the location.

3.7 People

According to (Andriyanto et al., 2020) explains that humans have a fundamental responsibility to comply with the rules when providing services to consumers in order to foster customer loyalty involved in long-term interactions with consumers to provide feedback is very important in fostering loyalty.

3.8 Process

According to (Andriyanto et al., 2020) Process is a method used from start to finish to determine results and then explain products to customers. The process also refers to business, efforts to plan and carry out its activities to meet the needs and desires of its customers.

3.9 Physical Evidence

Environmental characteristics are the most important factors in a situation. Including geographical locations such as buildings, decorations, rooms, sounds, aromas, lights, weather, placement and clean environments or most importantly as objects. Physical evidence includes, among others, the physical environment, physical construction, furniture/equipment, equipment, logos, colors and other items related to the services provided such as tickets, covers, labels and so on. According to Hendri and Sumanto, (220; 2010) in (Nuruddin Firdaus, 2018).

3.10 Competitive Advantage

According to Kotler and Armstrong in (Nuruddin Firdaus, 2018) explains the advantage over competitors achieved by offering cheaper value or even by offering greater benefits because the price is high.

3.12 Small and Medium Enterprises (SME)

Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) are stated in Law Number 20 of 2008 concerning Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. Article 1 paragraph 2 states that Small Business is a productive economic business that stands alone, which is carried out by individuals or business entities that are not subsidiaries or branches of companies that are owned, controlled, or become part either directly or indirectly of Medium Enterprises or Large Enterprises that meet the criteria of Small Enterprises.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Interview Results of UD Sanjaya Owner

Related to the development of the marketing strategy concept applied by UD Sanjaya to dry noodle products and based on an interview with Mr. Gunawan as the owner of UD Sanjaya on October 28, 2024.

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"In making this sale, we usually only use offline marketing and God willing, in the near future we have plans to use social media as one of our marketing strategies too. The products we currently market are only in the Lampung area, especially the Bandar Lampung, South Lampung, North Lampung, Pringsewu, Pesawaran areas. Because for dry noodle snacks, only UD Sanjaya produces them, it is likely that UD Sanjaya will become the only SME that supplies dry noodle products in 5 regencies in Lampung Province. For dry noodle products, they can be consumed by all levels of society, because we sell products that have a taste that all levels of society can enjoy, so that everyone can consume them, both adults and children".

To reach the target market, the company must carry out a marketing mix strategy to expand its marketing. As for the marketing strategy, the company must pay attention to several aspects. such as Products, Prices, Distribution, Promotion, People, Processes, Physical Evidence. As stated by Mr. Gunawan as the owner of UD Sanjaya on October 28, 2024:

"In every region, there must be many who supply dry noodle products both from outside the Province and its surroundings, so our competitors are also quite numerous and well-known, therefore we also need to market products in our own marketing strategy. As for the products we sell, promotions from customers to other customers or even through social media which of course must be in accordance with our business, the distribution channels that we must determine, the prices that we set, the production process that we maintain, the people or human resources that we always provide training, and physical evidence such as product appearance and company identity that we maintain".

Based on the results of interviews and observations conducted by researchers, the marketing strategy concept developed by UD Sanjaya to increase competitive advantage is by using social media as one of the promotional tools to market products at UD Sanajaya. Creating social media accounts specifically for UD Sanjaya products such as Instagram, Tiktok, Shoppe and others.

4.2 Product

UD Sanajaya pays close attention to the quality of its products, from raw materials, packaging, product identity and services. So it is very important for business people when they implement marketing strategies to increase customer interest or even distributors. What is the strategy for determining the quality of Dry Noodle products at UD Sanjaya and how to ensure that the products produced are consistent in terms of quality. As stated by Mr. Gunawan as the owner of UD Sanjaya on October 28, 2024:

"Product quality is also our top priority. Therefore, the first step we take is to ensure that every raw material we use must be of the best quality. We also work with suppliers who are trusted to provide raw materials such as flour, spices and other additional ingredients needed by UD Sanjaya. Sometimes we also do not hesitate to reject raw materials that do not meet our standards. The production process itself uses modern machines that are able to maintain consistency at every stage, from mixing ingredients to frying, packaging, everything is strictly supervised by an experienced production team. In addition, we also implement a quality control system. Each

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batch of our products is tested first before being released to the market. This test also includes checking the taste, texture, color of the noodles and the raw materials of the spices. To maintain the consistency of product quality, we also involve consumers by asking for feedback through surveys after they consume our products. This input from consumers is the basis for us to continue to innovate and maintain quality standards. We believe that maintaining quality is the main key to winning the competition in the market”.

Are there any product innovations or variations in the taste of dry noodles offered to attract more consumers. As stated by Mr. Gunawan as the owner of UD Sanjaya on October 28, 2024:

“Yes, that's right, we will always try to innovate both in terms of taste and our products. In addition, we also plan to add flavors that combine local and international flavors. We hope that this innovation can attract more consumers and increase our sales and we want to be one of the main choices for those looking for snacks such as the dry noodle products that we have with various flavors.”

In what way does UD Sanjaya ensure that employees play a very important role in ensuring product quality is maintained. As stated by Mr. Gunawan as the owner of UD Sanjaya on October 28, 2024:

“At UD Sanjaya, we also believe that employees are the same as very important assets in maintaining product quality. In addition, we also provide training to employees on what the quality standards of UD Sanjaya products are and what good production techniques are for the company. Furthermore, training also greatly helps employees to understand how important quality is in every production carried out at UD Sanjaya. We also have a monitoring system that involves employees in every production. They are responsible for checking the quality of raw materials and final products every day and every time they want to produce. We also provide space for employees to always report any problems they encounter during production so that we can also take action or decisions immediately. Our hope is to continue to involve employees in every aspect of production. We also want them to always feel that they are part of the UD Sanjaya family too, so that they have a sense of caring about the quality of the products we produce.”

Based on the results of interviews and observations conducted by researchers. If the products provided by UD Sanjaya are very numerous, not only dry noodle products, there are still many other products. As the discussion above explained by Lupiyoadi, in (Nuruddin Firdaus, 2018) Product is any item or process that offers added value to customers. One thing to note in product development is that consumers do not only buy physical goods from the company that sells them, they also provide other benefits.

4.3 Price

Pricing refers to a policy that concerns a certain amount of money that customers want to buy a product. Therefore, in determining the price, a check needs to be carried out to determine what factors influence it, one method is by checking the market to determine the value or price of a product provided by UD Sanjaya. So that the price given to customers is still affordable for the product provided. Next is the marketing strategy used by

the company to determine the price of the products offered. As stated by Mr. Gunawan as the owner of UD Sanjaya on October 28, 2024, he said:

“We set prices based on calculations including production costs, including raw materials, labor and distribution. We also consider the market price of similar products and try to offer competitive prices without sacrificing quality. I believe that affordable prices but still in line with high quality are one of the keys to surviving and excelling in the market. We also sometimes give discounts or special prices for large purchases, so that consumers feel they get more value from our products. As for the selling price per ball, we sell it at a price of IDR. 36,500.” The results of the observation showed the same results as the results of the interview by the researcher, that UD Sanjaya in setting product prices according to existing provisions. The pricing strategy used by UD Sanjaya explains that prices are flexible, meaning that they can be quickly adjusted to take into account market changes. Many competitors in the same business will not reduce the sales performance of dry noodle products in particular and Mr. Gunawan said that he would not sell his products at high prices but with decreasing quality, so with the quality of the product and the price sold it might be competitive with other sellers.

4.4 Promotion

Promotion is one of the common strategies used by companies to attract consumers to the products sold. What is the promotional strategy used to increase sales of dry noodles at UD Sanjaya, as stated by Mr. Gunawan as the owner of UD Sanjaya on October 28, 2024:

"The promotional strategy that we have done is just word of mouth and we offer it to every agent, besides that we are also actively participating in SME exhibitions where we can introduce products directly to new consumers and we also work with several distributors in each region. We are also planning promotions through other social media. Sometimes we also give free samples at local events as part of our strategy to increase brand awareness." Has the promotional strategy carried out by UD Sanjaya attracted the attention of the target market? And are there any special promotional programs that are effective in increasing sales volume. As stated by Mr. Gunawan as the owner of UD Sanjaya on October 28, 2024:

"We have several special promotional programs such as discounts for purchases in certain quantities, usually wholesale stores and large agents. We are also always looking for ways to innovate to launch more interactive promotional campaigns and not only that, we are trying to let the public know that UD Sanjaya also has dry noodle products and has many flavor variants, besides that, what is a PR for us is that dry noodle products are not only from outside, but in the area they also produce specifically for the Lampung area.”

The results of the interview showed the same results as the results of observations related to the promotion carried out by UD Sanjaya which included word of mouth and offering to each agent, this was done to establish good relations with customers.

4.5 Distribution

Distribution is a process carried out by a company to ensure that its products reach customers. As done by UD Sanjaya itself. The following is a statement from Mr. Gunawam as the owner of UD Sanjaya on October 28, 2024 regarding distribution:

“We have several distribution channels in each region such as Pringsewu, Pesawaran, South Lampung, Bandar Lampung, North Lampung. We also work with local distributors so that our products can reach more consumers in more distant areas. We realize the importance of being present in various distribution channels, because consumers now have many choices of places to shop. Our products are available in stalls, wholesale stores, traditional markets, besides that we also develop distribution through online platforms such as marketplaces and social media. Currently, our distribution wants to cover areas outside the island. However, of course there are challenges in distribution, especially related to shipping costs to more distant areas. We try to overcome this by finding efficient logistics partners and managing stock at several strategic distribution points to minimize shipping time.”

Is there a strategy for choosing a location or sales area so that consumers can more easily buy products. As stated by Mr. Gunawan as the owner of UD Sanjaya on October 28, 2024:

“Of course, we also do not carelessly collect data on shopping habits and consumer preferences in various regions. This method really helps us to choose a strategic location, be it in a shop or a traditional market. We also focus sales in areas with high populations and good accessibility. In addition, we also really consider areas that have an interest in dry noodle products, such as areas with a strong culinary culture. We also build partnerships with local distributors to expand our market reach.”

The results of the interview above explain the same results as the results of observations by researchers, and show that UD Sanjaya is indeed in a strategic location where it is on the Sumatra cross-country road, easily accessible from various directions, close to the toll road. Referring to the theory explained by Tjiptono in (Nuruddin Firdaus, 2018) which states that selecting a physical location requires careful consideration of the following factors such as ease of access, visibility, traffic, ample parking, environment, competition or competitors.

4.6 Process

Talking about the process also includes the steps of procedures, mechanisms, activities and routines that ensure a product can satisfy customers. Regarding the process of production and distribution at UD Sanjaya, are there any plans to increase the efficiency of the process. The following is a statement from Mr. Gunawam as the owner of UD Sanjaya on October 28, 2024:

“We run the production process with strict operational standards. Every stage of production, from raw material processing to packaging, is supervised by a quality control team. We also use technology that helps increase the efficiency of the production process without sacrificing product quality. For distribution, we use an integrated ordering system, so we can monitor stock in real time and manage shipments faster. This is important so that products are always available to consumers, especially when demand increases.”

Based on the results of interviews and observations, it can be seen that efficiency in the production and distribution process can help UD Sanjaya in meeting consumer demand well. Controlling quality and ensuring that products remain consistent will increase consumer confidence and make the market more competitive.

4.7 People

Based on the results of research in optimizing service to UD Sanjaya consumers who always prioritize friendliness and maximum service quality, because these elements are a type of service that makes customers or employees feel happy. What is the role of employees in supporting the success of the marketing strategy at UD Sanjaya, and is there any special training for UD Sanjaya employees themselves. The following is a statement from Mr. Gunawam as the owner of UD Sanjaya on October 28, 2024:

“In our opinion, employees are an important part of the marketing strategy. Because they are trained to provide friendly and helpful service to consumers, both in stores and through social media. We provide regular training so that they have good communication skills and knowledge of the product. This helps build consumer trust and satisfaction. We also involve employees in product promotions, such as managing social media accounts and helping at events organized by the company. In this way, employees feel more involved in the success of the company and become more enthusiastic in supporting marketing activities.”

The results of this interview show the same results as the observation results which show that every UD Sanjaya employee always behaves quickly, politely and neatly. Because with a neat appearance, it makes employees enthusiastic about working and based on the description above, trained Human Resources (HR) have a positive impact on the company's image. Effective service increases customer satisfaction and fosters loyalty, which is an important stage of UD Sanjaya's competitive advantage.

4.7 Physical Evidence

Overall, physical evidence includes other statements about the product that are directly related to the product being sold. According to Lupiyoadi in (Nuruddin Firdaus, 2018) explains that a physical form that directly interacts with consumers and helps marketing in promoting business in the market and providing tangible support related to the location. It can be seen that this physical evidence indirectly greatly influences consumers' decisions to buy the products offered. Furthermore, how does UD Sanjaya maintain its product image through packaging and brand identity. The following is a statement from Mr. Gunawam as the owner of UD Sanjaya on October 28, 2024:

“We use a simple but attractive packaging design, with a distinctive logo and color that is easily recognizable. We also ensure that our packaging is practical and maintains the quality of the product inside. Our visual identity reflects the values of quality and trust that we build with consumers. In addition to packaging, we always strive to create a positive consumer experience by maintaining product quality and good service, so that consumers have a positive impression every time they buy our products.”

In your opinion, what makes UD Sanjaya products different and superior to other competitors?

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“I think quality and competitive prices are our main advantages. In addition, we also have a wider variety of products than our competitors, so consumers can choose according to their taste. In addition to product quality, our service is also an added value. We always try to provide fast and responsive service, especially for consumers who buy online. We also establish good relationships with our distribution partners and consumers, because we believe that consumer satisfaction is the most important thing in this business. Support from loyal consumers also gives us more strength to continue to grow and compete in an increasingly competitive market.”

From the results of interviews and observations, it shows that ud sanjaya's packaging is very varied, the production site is very clean, spacious and comfortable. from the production site to the packaging, everything is neatly arranged. Conclusion the conclusion contains a brief summary of the research results and a discussion that answers the research objectives.

5. Conclusion

Based on what has been studied by researchers, it can be concluded that the marketing mix strategy at UD Sanjaya in Natar District, South Lampung Regency, is explained as follows: 1. Conclusion from the analysis of the marketing mix strategy on competitive advantages at UD Sanjaya, especially in dry noodle products. It can be said that UD Sanjaya is currently facing significant challenges in maximizing its market potential. Because the dry noodle products offered by UD Sanjaya have good quality and are able to meet consumer needs, the lack of social media presence and others. The main obstacle in increasing sales volume is in terms of price, UD Sanjaya also needs to ensure that the dry noodles produced are not only of good quality but also have attractive flavor variants for consumers. Developing dry noodle products with different flavors or more distinctive packaging designs will help attract more customers, or a wider market. In addition, it is very important for UD Sanjaya to provide clear information about the advantages of its products, such as the raw materials used and the manufacturing process using modern machines and that is a way to increase appeal in the eyes of consumers. In terms of place or distribution, it is also an important factor in the marketing mix, and UD Sanjaya's place is very proportional and easy to find. In addition, building partnerships with local shops or agents can help increase product distribution and availability in the market. In terms of promotion, a more aggressive and creative marketing strategy is needed. Although UD Sanjaya is still promoting offline and by word of mouth. UD Sanjaya will soon utilize social media and other channels for its promotional media. This will help increase brand awareness and business development, presence on digital platforms will be very important to attract market segments that are easier and more tech-savvy. Overall, to achieve competitive advantage, UD Sanjaya must implement all elements in the marketing mix by maintaining quality, setting competitive prices, expanding distribution channels, and implementing effective promotional strategies. Adaptation and innovation will be key to exploiting market potential and achieving sustainable success. 2. The solution to overcome the obstacles faced by UD Sanjaya in marketing dry noodle products in implementing the marketing mix strategy is by always innovating to add flavor variants and not being stagnant on that flavor alone. Carrying out promotions using

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social media Instagram and other channels uploading attractive dry noodle products, creating content according to current trends so that consumers are interested when they see content from UD Sanjaya. With social media, UD Sanjaya's marketing target is also getting wider, not only in certain areas but can reach the outside market.

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